

As on 04-02-2020, the following data entry protocol is recommended in order to add record on crop management into the knowledge base system. Crop management consists of four main tables; i) Nutrient application, ii) Planting, iii) Pest/Weed/Disease Control and iv) Cropping system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning of the crops. The sources may be review papers, databases and web articles. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

i) Nutrient application

1. There are nine fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Fertiliser (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the type of fertiliser that is applied for a specific crop
- The type of fertiliser shall be recorded in an option table 'Opt Fertilisers'. In the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection.

1.3 Application Time (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the time of fertiliser application according to the crops growth stages.
- The source **MUST** indicate at which crop stage the fertiliser is applied.
- The application time is recorded in an option table 'Opt Crop Stage'. In the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection.
- The application time options are fixed as below:
 - i) Germination - Time when seed starts to germinate to become seedling
 - ii) Pre-planting - Fertiliser was applied on the soil before crop being planted.
 - iii) Vegetative - Stage that occurs after germination and before flowering, during which the plant develops the majority of its foliage and truly flourishes.
 - iv) Reproductive - Time when crops are physiologically capable of commencing the production of reproductive parts: flowers, fruits and seeds.
 - v) Ripening - Time when the developmental stage of fruits and seeds to ripen.

1.4 Application Rate Unit

- This is referring to the unit used when applying the fertiliser. E.g. kg/ha, %.

1.5 Amount Max, Mean, Min

- This is referring to the recommended maximum, mean and minimum amount of fertiliser that is applied on a specific crop.

1.6 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the nutrient application on crop itself.

1.7 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

Reference:

Cropsreview.com. (2019). Development in Plants: How Plants Grow from Seeds. Retrieved from <https://www.cropsreview.com/development-in-plants.html>

ii) Planting

1. There are 17 fields to be entered, three of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Preferred Planting Material (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the type of material used to grow the crop
- The planting material is entered in text and **MUST NOT MORE** than 100 words.

1.3 Require Transplanting

- This is to indicate the crop planting material requires transplanting to other space after its establishment or not.
- This is answer one of two choices, which is yes or no selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

1.3 Planting Rate Unit

- This is referring to the planting material unit used in specific areas. E.g. kg/ha

1.4 Planting Rate (Min Max)

- This is referring to the maximum and minimum number of vegetative propagation parts or seeds planted according to the 'Planting Rate Unit' field.

1.5 Spacing Between Plants (Max and Min)

- This is referring maximum and minimum distance between a plant to another plant
- The recorded value **MUST** be in centimeter (cm).

1.6 Spacing Between Rows (Max and Min)

- This is referring to the maximum and minimum distance between a row of planted crop to another row.
- The recorded value **MUST** be in centimeter (cm)

1.7 Planting Depth (Max and Min)

- This is referring to the maximum and minimum depth of sowing the planting materials.
- The recorded value **MUST** be in centimeter (cm)

1.8 Require Structure

- This field is to store information if the crop required additional supporting structure to grow e.g. poles, greenhouse, fence, etc.

1.9 Special Care

- This field is to store information on crop special care

2.0 Available Mechanisation

- This field is to store information if the planting process is using machine e.g. tractor

2.1 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop planting itself.

2.2 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

iii) Pest/Weed/Disease control

1. There are eight fields to be entered, three of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 PWD Name

- PWD Name is referring to the Pest, Weed or Disease Name that may affect that crop.
 - i) Pest is an organism living and growing where they are not wanted and can cause damage to plants, humans, structures, and other creatures, including crops that are grown for food
 - ii) Weed is a plant that is growing in the wrong place. Weeds take valuable space, water, sunlight and nutrients that may otherwise be accessible to important crops.

iii) A plant disease is defined as anything that prevents a plant from performing to its maximum potential. This definition is broad and includes abiotic and biotic plant diseases.

1.3 PWD Type (Compulsory)

- User have to choose the type of PWD whether Pest, Disease or Weed that already affected the crops.
- In the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection.

1.4 Causal Agent

- This is referring to the any agent that give effect or is responsible for disease such as a virus, parasite, fungus, or bacterium

1.5 Symptoms

- This is referring to the reaction or any physical or biological changes that happened to the crops one it was affected by the Pest, Weed or Disease.

1.6 Control

- This is referring to the ways to control the Pest, Weed or Disease symptoms. The control can help to stop the disease dispersal or to prevent from the crops being affected.

1.8 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the pest/weed/disease on crop itself.

1.9 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

References:

- Gale, L. (2004). Pests and Diseases. Retrieved from <https://www.pitchcare.com/news-media/pests-and-diseases.html>
- Institute of Agriculture and Natural Resources. (n.d) Plant Disease: Pathogens and Cycles. Retrieved from <https://cropwatch.unl.edu/soybean-management/plant-disease>
- PennState Extension. (2016). Pests and Pesticides in Agriculture. Retrieved from <https://extension.psu.edu/pests-and-pesticides-in-agriculture>

iv) Cropping system

1. There are five fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.

- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in the 'Crop' field. Since the common name is used,, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in 'Crop Records' table. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the source.

1.2 Introduced Crop (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop name that will be planted together with the selected crop in the 'Crop' field.
- Ensure there is **NO** previous record which has used the same crop in the 'Crop' field and in 'Introduced Crop' field.

1.3 Cropping System (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the type or sequence of growing crops.
- User **MUST** choose one cropping system in one record, if there is more than one cropping system used for growing the crop, a new record **MUST** be created.
- The cropping system options are fixed as below:

i) Crop rotation:

Crops are changed in the field from year to year according to a planned sequence rather than the same crop being grown in the same field. The crop rotation can include both annual and perennial crops which are seeded for several years.

ii) Multiple cropping:

Two or more crops grown in the same field within a given year. Annual and perennial plants can be organized in fields together. Another example might be planting rows of fruit trees with cereal grains or vegetables in between and windbreaks planted around the field perimeter.

iii) Mixed cropping:

Two or more crops are mixed together in the same field at the same time without definite row arrangement. Complementary crops include oats and peas or mixtures of forage grasses and legumes.

iv) Monocropping:

This is where the field is used to grow only one crop season after season.

v) Sequential Cropping:

This involves growing two crops in the same field, one after the other in the same year. In some places, the rainy season is long enough to grow two crops: either two main crops, or one main crop followed by a cover crop. Growing two crops may also be possible if there are two rainy seasons, or if there is enough moisture left in the soil to grow a second crop. If the crops are different, this is a crop rotation.

E.g. planting maize in the long rains, then beans during the short rains.

vi) Intercropping:

This means growing two or more crops in the same field at the same time.

E. g. planting alternating rows of maize and beans or growing a cover crop in between the cereal rows.

vii) Strip cropping:

This involves planting broad strips of several crops in the field. E.g. planting alternating strips of maize, soybean and finger millet.

ix) Relay cropping:

This is growing one crop, then planting another crop (usually a cover crop) in the same field before harvesting the first. This helps avoid competition between the main crop and the intercrop. It also uses the field for a longer time, since the cover crop usually continues to grow after the main crop is harvested.

E.g. planting maize, then sowing beans between the maize rows four weeks later.

1.5 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the cropping system on crop itself.

1.6 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

References:

- Blanco-Canqui, H., & Lal, R. (2010) Cropping Systems. In: Principles of Soil Conservation and Management. Springer, Dordrecht. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8709-7_7
- REAP Canada. (2003). Introduction to Ecological Farming : Farmer-to-Farmer Participatory Training Course. Retrieved from [https://www.reap-canada.com/online_library/Reports%20and%20Newsletters/International%20Development/19e%20Cropping%20Systems%20\(English\).pdf](https://www.reap-canada.com/online_library/Reports%20and%20Newsletters/International%20Development/19e%20Cropping%20Systems%20(English).pdf)
- Conservation Agriculture. (n.d.). Chapter 6: Crops and cropping systems. Retrieved from <http://www.act-africa.org/image/06CROP~1.PDF>